

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF MUSIC CREATION OF BLACK PEOPLE IN MUSIC EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article discusses the scientific-theoretical significance of Karakalpak folk music in improving the professional training of future music culture teachers.

Key words: Karakalpak folk music creation, music culture, professional competence, methodology.

Music has the ability to influence the moral and ethical aspects of the soul. As long as music has such characteristics, it should be included among the means of educating young people." The role of our musical heritage is also important in this regard, as the national program requires the training of highly qualified personnel who respond to highly moral and ethical students. While getting acquainted with the heritage of Uzbek folk music in music culture lessons, we learn about the historical path of the hardworking people, traditions, rituals, friendship, heroism, love for the Motherland, love - loyalty, justice. we will have a broad understanding.

The Autonomous Republic of Karakalpakstan, which has been part of Uzbekistan since 1936, borders Kazakhstan in the north and Turkmenistan in the south. In these endless deserts where the continental climate prevails, folk art is passed down from generation to generation with the help of gifts and donations. Jirov is a performer of heroic epics. He glorifies the courage and strength of the hero. His throaty voice and thick voice match his voice. The voice and voice of Jirov, the values praised in his epics lead the listener to the legendary world of nomadic peoples and steppes. Bakhshi performs in a completely different scene. He sings epics that glorify love. His sagas tell the story of the adventures of lovers on their way to find each other. Bakhshi sings with her own voice accompanied by dutor. His vocal cords, musical instruments, and the theme of his epics embody more legends and dreams of the settled peoples of Central Asia. At this point, it should be noted that the musical culture of Karakalpak bakhshis is based on these two traditions, which do not contradict each other, but complement each other.

Usually, telling a story lasts for several hours, and sometimes even several nights. In the past, weddings could not be imagined without the participation of bakhshi or jirov. His performance was considered the most important part of the event. While the listeners were gathering around the fire, they were tuning the

bakhshi drum, recording the sound of their fingers, and performing terms such as "Noma Boshi" (1, 20). Then he adjusted his voice and sang from admonitions and fertilizing hymns (5, 8, 12). After the audience had gathered, an elder asked them which saga they would like to hear. After the listeners chose the epic, the elder recited the blessing and the bakhshi began to perform. In these times, television, radio and other entertainment technologies have not yet entered people's daily life, and the story of bakhshi can be treated like a movie. Under the tones of his voice, heroes were born or died, experienced various adventures, and the listeners forgot the passage of time. Each bakhshi had its own musical, storytelling method, and actions similar to the words to interest and attract the audience, to make the performance live, to make them cry and laugh in accordance with the events being told.

Bakhshi has a very important position in traditional Karakalpak society. He is the owner of a legacy that is passed down from generation to generation. Above all, giving is a carrier of memory. This memory consists of elements from historical and mythological sources. Thus, this memory serves to understand the national identity. On top of that, Bakhshi is a skilled artist, and will forever emphasize his gratitude to his teacher who taught him this skill. The unique musical aesthetics of performing epics was laid by famous teachers of the past, such as Aqimbet, Musa, Suvej, Genjebai. And finally, bakhshi has a social function of conveying moral values to the listeners. Bakhshi is an example not only to his students, but also to the public who are ready to listen to his voice and wisdom.

Undoubtedly, the technical and socio-cultural development of recent decades has significantly reduced the social status of bakhshis, as well as the scope of performance. Now their performances at foreign concerts, various festivals and contests, and national holidays are limited in time and rarely last more than 10 minutes. On top of that, as a result of the fundamental changes that took place in the 20th century, sound-amplifying devices are increasingly taking the place of bakhshis at weddings. In this situation, some Bakhshis tried to perform traditional music in the way of pop music. Others, on the contrary, started to restore entire sagas from old audio tapes (G. Allambergenova, J. Piyazov). Regardless, the number of students studying at the Nukus College of Art, founded in 1991, under teachers such as G. Otemuratov, T. Qalliev, K. Tinibaev, B. Sirimbetov has increased in recent years. is increasing. This interest among young people undoubtedly shows that worthy substitutes are emerging from them. As a proof of this, it can be shown that they successfully participate in various contests, or that in 2010, in our project, many voices of young people

from different regions of Karakalpakstan were recorded. Thus, the release of this disc proves the immortality of the epic traditions of the Karakalpak people, pays tribute to the most important people in society, and also to their ancestors, which have been preserved from mouth to mouth for centuries. We hope that it will help young people to protect their horses.

As we analyze the issues of studying Karakalpak national music, we understand that the scientific works and research processes that should be studied in the field are not yet at the level of demand. We lack specialists. We need to support the existing experts to a certain extent. If we take into account that it has not been more than 20 years since the opening of higher education institutions related to the field in our country, we believe that our mature scientists-intellectuals who will perfectly study the field will grow up. This is the demand of the times!

One of the main goals of the educational system is to prepare future music teachers for spiritual and educational activities. From the above comments, we can say that the role of the science of music culture in the education system is very important. In order for music culture teachers to be active in spiritual and educational work, they are given the necessary knowledge and skills in higher education institutions

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